

IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN BONE REGENERATION IN PATIENTS WITH CLOSED FRACTURES OF TUBULAR BONES

Napasov Ilkhomjon Zubaydullovich

Samarkand State Medical University

ilhom.napasov@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10974449>

Annotation

A clinical and immunological comparison of the course of regenerative processes of bone tissue, conducted on the basis of comparing the data of ultrasound examination of the fracture zone and the information obtained from monitoring changes in immunological parameters of blood, revealed a number of features of the immunological reaction of the body. This, to a certain extent, reflects the peculiarities of the course of bone tissue regeneration, which can be interpreted as possible effective prognostic markers. To carry out such an assessment, the most effective may be the application of principles and analyses based on the rules of evidence-based medicine.

Keywords: regeneration, bone tissue, immunity

Relevance. It is believed that a violation of bone regeneration in closed fractures of tubular bones, leading to the formation of a false joint, occurs in about 2% of all fractures (1,3), but with certain injuries this violation can reach 20%.

The main problems associated with impaired bone regeneration in closed fractures of tubular bones are associated with prolonged pain syndrome, loss of limb function and mental stress conditions (5,7,23). In recent decades, scientists have focused on studying the close relationship between the immune system and bone tissue. So much close attention has led to the emergence of a new term – osteoimmunology (3,2). To date, it has been convincingly proven that most components of the immune system, including numerous molecules, cytokines, chemokines, hormones, receptors and transcription factors, etc. have a close connection with the regenerative processes of bone tissue. Moreover, studies were conducted under both physiological and pathological conditions (4,11,19,20).

To date, it is already known that the main immune cells interact with bone tissue as the main components of the system, and sometimes as auxiliary ones. In particular, it became known that T cells, as well as their auxiliary components, are actively involved in the regeneration of bone tissue and their auxiliary cells. First of all, this directly concerns the formation of the osteoclastogenesis process (9,18,23).

There is information regarding the controlled role of cytokines in the process of bone tissue regeneration. Specific morphogenetic proteins and cytokines of tumor necrosis factor determine the process of bone regeneration (6,8,14).

Inhibition of T cell activation suppresses induced T cell expression, which leads to inhibition of osteoclastogenesis (10,13,21). It has been proven that T cells can influence osteoclastogenesis both indirectly and directly through the active secretion of IL-17, which leads to the secretion of TNF- α and IL-1, which, in turn, support osteoclastogenesis (4,12,17).

The purpose of the study: to study the indicators of cellular and humoral immunity during bone regeneration in patients with closed fractures of tubular bones.

Material and methods. The results of a comprehensive examination and treatment of 226 patients with closed fractures of long tubular bones are analyzed. All patients were treated and examined at the Samarkand branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Traumatology and Orthopedics from 2017 to 2022 inclusive.

We divided the clinical material into two groups: the control and the main one. The main group of patients consisted of 112 patients in whom clinical and immunological monitoring was used to predict bone tissue regeneration using the IPBR program developed by us ("Method for predicting bone tissue regeneration"). In the control group, against the background of the use of traditional methods for assessing bone tissue regeneration, the main parameters of cellular and humoral immunity were studied. The patients of young and mature age (61.5%) were male (77.4%).

In the control group of patients in 71.1%, and in the main group in 74.1% of cases, the treatment of patients was for a closed fracture of the tibia. The remaining patients had closed femoral fractures (28.9% and 25.9%, respectively). In the control and main groups, household and street injuries were the main causes of tubular bone fractures (44.7% and 49.1%, respectively). The classification of M.E. Muller et al. was used in the diagnosis. (1996).

The research methods were comprehensive and conducted in accordance with the regulations approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan standards of medical care for traumatological and orthopedic patients.

Results and discussion: Analyzing the data on monitoring changes in cellular immunity during bone regeneration, it can be noted that in patients of the first subgroup, the uncomplicated course of bone regeneration was accompanied by

a stable curve. At the same time, in patients of the second subgroup, regenerative processes of bone tissue, after a fracture, occurred with a double leveling in relation to the dynamics of patients of the first subgroup.

Leveling occurred during the development of a local purulent-inflammatory process, including osteomyelitis in the range of CD3+ T lymphocytes in the blood from 51.31% to 60.32%. Such a variation in the number of CD3+ T lymphocytes in the blood in patients of the second subgroup, apparently, made it possible to achieve normal consolidation of bone fracture even after suffering from chronic local purulent inflammatory disease. However, in patients of the third subgroup, the absence of recurrent leveling, unfortunately, did not lead to normal bone regeneration.

The clinical and immunological comparison of the course of regenerative processes of bone tissue, carried out on the basis of comparing the data of ultrasound examination of the fracture zone and the information obtained from monitoring changes in immunological parameters of blood, allowed us to identify a number of features of the immunological reaction of the body. This, to a certain extent, reflects the peculiarities of the course of bone tissue regeneration, which can be interpreted as possible effective prognostic markers. To carry out such an assessment, the most effective may be the application of principles and analyses based on the rules of evidence-based medicine

Conclusions:

1. Drawing parallels between changes in phagocytic activity and the number of phagocytes, a certain correspondence can be noted. With a stable number of macrophages, the activity index changed in patients with different outcomes of bone regeneration, which indicates an activation of functional activity over hematopoietic, which, apparently, was associated with the transfer of cell formation towards osteoclasts and osteoblasts.

2. Clinical and immunological comparison of the course of regenerative processes of bone tissue, conducted on the basis of comparing the data of ultrasound examination of the fracture zone and the information obtained from monitoring changes in immunological parameters of blood, revealed a number of features of the immunological reaction of the body. This, to a certain extent, reflects the peculiarities of the course of bone tissue regeneration, which can be interpreted as possible effective prognostic markers. To carry out such an assessment, the most effective may be the application of principles and analyses based on the rules of evidence-based medicine.

Literature:

1. Belokhvostikova T.S. Cytokine regulation of osteogenesis // Byul. VSNTS SB RAMS. Irkutsk: "NTO NCRVH VSNC SB RAMS", 1999;1(9):Pp.147-152.
2. New perspectives on bone tissue regeneration in atrophy and defects of jaw bone tissue / A. Yu. Ryabov, M. V. Lekishvili // Topical issues of tissue and cell transplantology : Collection of abstracts on VII All-Russian Symposium with International participation, Astrakhan, April 27-28, 2017. – Astrakhan: Astrakhan State Medical University, 2017. – pp. 10-11.
3. Experimental substantiation of the use of combined biomaterials for bone tissue regeneration / S. M. Hefzollesan, F. Y. Mammadov, G. G. Musayeva, A.M. Mammadov // Bulletin of dentistry. - 2022. – Volume 120, No. 3. – pp. 76-82.
4. Bal Z., Kushioka J., Kodama J., Kaito T., Yoshikawa H., Korkusuz P., Korkusuz F. The use and release of BMP and TGF β in bone regeneration. Turk J Med Sci. 2020, November 3;50(SI-2): 1707-1722.
5. Human lactoferrin interacts with soluble CD14 and inhibits the expression of endothelial adhesion molecules, E-selectin and ICAM-1 induced by the CD14 - lipopolysaccharide complex / S. Bavey, E. Ellass, D.G. Fernig, S. Blankwart et al. // J. Infect Immun. – 2020;68:Pp.6519-6S2S.

